

Challenges that Active and Assisted Living Programme research projects working on digital solutions for older adults need to be aware of

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Author Note

The work was supported by the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS/CCCDI - UEFISCDI (Executive Unit for the Financing of Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation), based on funding contract no. 61/2021, within the Project "Increasing the research capacity and the national and international visibility of the Ana Aslan International Foundation (FAAI), including through a better promotion of the results obtained (SMART-BEAR)", code PN-III-P3-3.6- H2020-2020-0174.

No prior dissemination of the ideas and data appearing in the manuscript has been carried out.

The authors report no competing interests.

Neither the design, hypotheses, nor the analytic plan for this study were preregistered.

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Older adults represent an increasing proportion of the population. The World Health Organisation predicts that 1 in 6 people will be aged 60 years or over by 2030 (World Health Organisation, 2022). Many older adults have, or may face as they advance in age, complex health needs. Needs which require that they, or various medical staff, routinely travel to access, or deliver health services. The public sectors' financial constraints, together with the current economic downturn are leading to increasing financial pressures which require that healthcare and social-care service providers identify alternative, more efficient, delivery models (Currie et al., 2015). This is where digital solutions, such as those developed through the European programme funding Active and Assisted Living Programme (AAL) may provide a means of overcoming some of these challenges. Digital solutions can support older adults and their formal and/or informal caregivers with performing daily activities, ageing in place, and/or compensate for functional disorders (Zarina et al., 2018). Growing evidence that the use of computers and tablets improves older adults social, emotional and cognitive abilities is becoming available (Mitzner et al., 2019). These can be related to measurable improvements in cognitive domains such as executive functioning, working memory, episodic memory but also in subjective reports related to quality of life, social support, and depression (Mitzner et al., 2019).

Solutions aimed for the management and prevention of medical (and medically related) conditions of older adults typically combine off the shelf products, services and environments which are build based on specialist knowledge of the ageing processes. Furthermore, these technologies enable the remote connection of elderly patients with their careers and healthcare professionals, thereby accomplishing a shift from the traditional institution-based form of healthcare, to a community-based one (Chen et al., 2013) and reduce the need for patients and healthcare providers to travel to attend/deliver in-person assessments.

A large number of digital solutions that enable remote assessment and management of various health issues have been developed. Recent research has shown that these may help older adults lead healthier, more independent, and more socially engaging lives (Zarina et al., 2018). Another benefit of digital assessment technology, which is of particular importance to health cares and researchers, is the granularity of the data that can be obtained from such an assesment. Particularly for those interested in evaluating the effect of medication to treat neurodegenerative disease (Libon et al., 2021). Timely neuropsychological evaluation is extremely important, not only as an outcome measure in evaluating whether the treatment is effective, but also to enable proper and more effective diagnosis (Libon et al., 2021). Digital solutions that are capable of flagging cognitive decline, early in the degeneration process, are of particular relevance to our activity, as the bulk of the projects that we have implemented as an organisation focus on this goal. Therefore, in this paper

we will discuss the opportunities and barriers of this type of technology and share some of our experiences relating to their development and field testing, using examples from our projects and the literature.

While digital assessment technology has many advantages, in terms of accessibility, richness of measurement, and cost (Germine et al., 2018), this technology is still at an early stage and faces several challenges. Tools that use digital assessment should have several important characteristics, including, but not limited to: leaving the construct of the measurement unchanged; uncover and measure behaviour not otherwise obtainable (e.g., via standard paper-and-pencil tests); the behaviour/s they uncover should be used to operationally define neurocognitive constructs (Libon et al., 2021). Proper piloting and research of digital assessments tools is also extremely important, however, this is at time treated lightly. This sometimes relates the limited time that AAL projects have for implementation, but also due to the false assumption that paper-and-pencil and their digital equivalent and will produce the same results (Clark, 1994). Many studies have found significant differences depending on the area that the test is measuring. Furthermore, proper piloting is also important in making sure that the software being developed is bug free and easy to use. Older adults tend to become discouraged when faced with technological bugs and related software issues, and perceive them as their own incompetence to operate systems. In many of our projects we run lab tests with the aim to ensure the safety and main functionalities of the digital systems, before providing them to primary older adults, but this is not always the case.

1. Challenges in the digitalisation of existing (paper-and-pencil) tests

Translating a paper-and-pencil test to digital format usually involves perceptual, cognitive and/or motor complexity changes to that tasks (Germine et al., 2018). Though this translation process can leave the construct of the measurement unchanged there are instances where changes in response modality may substantially threaten the tasks validity (Bailey et al., 2017). For example, evaluations that involve self-report (e.g., Geriatric Depression Scale, Mini Nutritional Assessment, etc.) are less likely to be changed conceptually (measure a different construct) when being converted to a digital format, compared to clinician rated evaluations (e.g., The clock drawing test, Rey–Osterrieth complex figure, Trail Making Test, etc.).

1.1. Digitalising the Clock Drawing Test (CDC)

The CDT is a widely used neuropsychological evaluation in dementia screening (Kaplan, 1988, 1990). There are several versions of this test, but in general they all ask that the participant draw the face of a clock (write all the numbers on the face of the clock in the appropriate position) and then draw the hands of the clock indicating a particular time (e.g., 10 after 11). Several digital versions of the CDT have been created (e.g., Müller et al., 2019, Davoudi et al., 2021a). Davoudi and

colleagues (2021a) tested participants diagnosed with Alzheimer’s Disease, vascular dementia, and healthy older adults using a digital version of the CDT. Using machine learning algorithms, they were able to classify participants into their respective groups using motor, kinematic and visuospatial features otherwise unobtainable (through CDT analogue version). Davoudi and colleagues (2021b) published a second paper that investigated “what exactly is a normal clock?”. The digital technology enabled them to measure various elements that are important in scoring the CDT, such as how participants drew the shape and size of the clock, as well as the digits and hands placement.

Our experience with digitalised versions of the CDT proved less fruitful. The way our IT partners decided to digitalise the test was by splitting the drawing task into subtasks (two consecutive screens). On the first screen the participant is presented with a circle with many indents/lines drawn onto it, and numbers from 1 to 12 they are asked to drag the numbers on the correct position on the circle (to form the face of a typical clock). After completing this first task (successfully or unsuccessfully) they are asked to place the hands of the clock so that they indicate 10 past 11. This way of assesment led to possible errors in both the first screen/assesment, and consequently in the second one. Achieving perfect alignment proved difficult during the field trials, as older adults don’t have the dexterity or the patience to align all the numbers, on a relatively small tablet screen. The IT department had informed us that their machine learning algorithm had “already learned what a perfect score is” (all numbers placed perfectly on the indents of their respective hour) and that it cannot “compromise” at this point. Because perfect alignment was not achieved on the first task (placing the numbers perfectly on the clock face), the second task (placing the hands on the clock) was also compromised. Clinical partners need to learn how to communicate medical information/neuropsychological in a simple manner that can be understood/implemented by IT partners.

1.2. Digitalising the Trail Making Test

A pertinent example of the possible complications that can arise when digitalising a clinician rated evaluation is given by Germine and colleagues (2018) using the Trail Making Test. The Trail Making Test is a commonly used evaluation of visual attention and task switching, which requires that the subject connects a set of circles with numbers and letters (alternating; Part B) in ascending order (Corrigan & Hinkeldey, 1987). In this test the dependent measure is the time the participant takes to connect the set of circles in the correct order. Performance on this task may depend on the medium being used. On a small touch screen (i.e., phone) the movements needed to connect the circles will be shorter, while on a bigger touch screen (i.e., tablet) these movements will be longer, with greater hand occlusion of the stimulus on smaller screens than larger screens, resulting in

different perceptual and motor challenges which may translate to better or worse performance (Germine et al., 2018). In one of the projects we have implemented, this task was done using a tablet. Rather than connecting the circles with a line (paper-and-pencil format) the participant has to tap the circles on the tablet screen in the indicated order. The speed with which the participant can complete this digital task is affected by variables that are unrelated to the cognitive domain that is being measured. Older adults have difficulties in operating touchscreens not simply because they are unfamiliar with the technology, but also because it is physically more difficult for them. Many older adults struggle with touch screens due to “leathery fingers”. As people age the moisture from our skin is gradually lost, hand and fingertips consequently also become dry which may hinder electricity passing through (No Isolation, 2022). These issues complicate both the implementation of these types of assesment as well as the interpretation of their results.

2. Challenges brought on by devices

Accuracy and precision of measurement varies depending on the digital device being used, on the hardware and software, all of which are beyond the control of the health carer and the patient (Germine et al., 2018). These confounding factors are rarely disseminated, or even documented, but they introduce variations in performance on behavioural measurements that are difficult to quantify. Germine and colleagues (2018) suggests that one of the biggest difference between digital devices is the duration it takes them to register user responses. This duration can be measured as the time between the user making a response (e.g. taps the tablet screen) and the registering of that response by the device. They further state that in this case the measured response time for any test is the user’s “real response time” plus the latency in response time due to the device, and that while this latency can be reduced through hardware and software improvements, it can never be completely eliminated.

In addition to variation brought by the medium being used (smartphone, tablet or PC, or even operating system IOS vs. Android), another barrier to digital neuropsychological assesment arises from the large variation in the relationship older adults have with devices. A study by Brahmandam and colleagues (2016) evaluated older adults willingness and ability to use a tablet in a clinical setting. In order to assess these two aspects, they approached 365 individuals in an emergency department in the US and asked them if they would be willing to fill in eight questions on the tablet instead of answering questions orally. 248 (68%) of the total 365 individuals approached were willing to take part. Out of the 248 participants that were included in the study, 75% were able to answer at least six of the 8 questions correctly, but only 12% were able to answer all 8 correctly. Furthermore only 29% of volunteers didn’t require any assistance. We also often find that while our volunteers declare that they can/are willing to test new technology, the majority of these volunteers

are not able to use it without assistance. This complicates the interpretation of digital evaluation that have been performed remotely, as it's possible that low scores on neuropsychological evaluations do not represent real cognitive impairment, but rather a digital "impairment".

3. Challenges brought on by wearables and auxiliary devices

Digital solutions for assessment and management developed by AAL consortia, are typically designed to be used together with different wearables. Wearables which are equipped with sensory and audio-visual technology which permit simultaneous collection of primary and secondary data (Onnela & Rauch, 2016) which enables the storing of valuable behavioural data that is typically not available in traditional neuropsychological assessment (Giannouli et al., 2018). Wearables can also support "active ageing" and consequently enhance quality of life (World Health Organization, 2021). Remote monitoring via wearables may sustain independence and help older adults in managing chronic conditions, as long as older adults use them as recommended (Ferguson et al., 2021).

Even though wearable devices bring many advantages to the monitoring and intervention of older adults health conditions (or in possibly preventing these), they raise a new set of challenges. Device setup, and maintenance, becomes more burdensome when a software application runs in parallel with wearable devices. Older adults need to remember/be able to charge all the devices, to check that the devices are still paired, and when these "un-pair" to be able to re-establish the connection between them. Moore and colleagues (2021) found that devices that required frequent charging, which consequently affected older adults routines and restricted the time that they can spend away from a power source, were viewed negatively. A recent meta-analysis by Moore and colleagues (2021) found that older adults are less likely to engage with devices that are perceived as burdensome or limit independence. Older adults perceived themselves as less independent when having to rely on family or friends to help them with technological issues (which, in our experience, is the case when having to pair devices).

David Conroy, professor of kinesiology at Penn State claims that a barrier of „current physical activity trackers [is that they] do not effectively identify and track older adults' activities. Wrist-worn devices are able to pick up steps, but they can also pick up other arm movements that could skew step counts." This measurement issue is even greater for older adults, as they typically walk slower so the signal from movement is subtler (Wagner, 2020). Wagner further proposes that we need to develop technology for older adults, devices should be able to recognize different types of activities relevant to their daily routines. Only then will wearable devices be able to "improve health and safety monitoring and create new possibilities for behavioural interventions to promote healthy aging" (Wagner, 2020).

Other barriers relate to the proper evaluation of digital devices. Have devices undergone testing which establishes that they are reliable measure of the construct under investigation? Our own experience relates to a project that had developed a digital system to monitor and improve frailty. One of the associated devices used with this system was meant to measure and train grip strength. No research had been done to evaluate if said device provided accurate and reliable measurements ensuring the validity of its grip strength evaluation. We therefore decided to run a pilot study (currently under review) assessing the inter-device reliability between that device and the gold standard toll in evaluating grip strength, the Jamar dynamometer. The device did show good-to-excellent inter-instrument reliability (with Jamar®) providing preliminary evidence that it can be used for objective assessment of grip strength. Still, when deciding which devices should be used as a training/monitoring solution for older adults AAL projects should make sure that these have been tested on that population.

4. Why are these solutions not adopted by older adults?

Even though digital health solutions are seen as potential means to reducing the rising care and pensions costs associated with an ageing population (Pirhonen et al., 2020) this kind of technology is still at a very early stage. Therefore, improving our knowledge of patient and carer needs and attitudes towards the acceptance of this technology is vital in it becoming part of a care package (Currie et al., 2015). These target groups need to be involved both in the development and implementation of digital health solutions, to be able to build solutions that are sensitive to their needs and the attributes specific to the society in which they live. These solutions should be easy to use, as patients and care staff (and sometimes even medical staff) are not always technologically literate. This is particularly true in Romania, and other less digitalised countries, where the older generation has not had early access to technology. While older adults usage of computers and the Internet are steadily increasing (67% of adults aged 65 years or older, in 2016 compared to 12% of older adults in 2000) their usage rates remain significantly lower compared to 90% of the general adult population (Mitzner et al., 2019). An earlier study by Alvseike and Brønnick (2012) found that cognitive decline and low self-efficacy are associated with the reduced use of technology by older adults. Acceptance of technology within the older group was linked to cognitive ability, those scoring higher on measures of fluid and crystallized intelligence were more likely to use technology, while higher levels of computer related anxiety predicted lower usage rates (Alvseike & Brønnick, 2012).

Apart from the objective technical barriers, older adults also face subjective barriers, depending on how they perceive their own technical skills. Ehn and colleagues (2018) looked at older adults experience in using activity monitors and found that low self-perceived efficacy in using technology

can influence their attitude and limit perceived ease of use of the device. Participants in their study mentioned that they were “worried about not being able to handle [the device]” (Ehn et al., 2018, p. 19). Such insecurities may be further exacerbated when older adults experience usability issues or technical failures but don’t have the knowledge to resolve the issue or sometimes even the capacity of identifying that this is a technical issue not their incorrect handling of the device.

The display and feedback of digital devices must align with the goal of its user and this may prove difficult as users have very different needs as well as abilities when it comes to interacting with devices. Some users only need a basic interface (e.g., a single button on a smart band that shows their step target). Others need more complex information to be displayed (more health monitoring goals on a smart band such as heart rate, sleep, etc.). If a device is not offering adequate feedback this can leave the user in feeling disconnected and undermine the effectiveness of the device. Our experience, as well as documented instances from the literature, shows that users ask for clear feedback about the different features and functions of the device they are using (e.g., what alerts are activated, who activated that alert – is it generated by the device or by a carer, and how they could disable it) (Moore et al., 2021).

Conclusion

This study wished to describe some of the challenges that AAL projects may face when designing digital solutions aimed for the evaluation of older adults health issues. With regard to neuropsychological evaluation, special attention needs to be given when wishing to digitalise pen-and paper tests, as several drawbacks have been highlighted in the literature. Not all tests are created equal, it may be easier, and less likely to conceptually change a test when digitalising a test that is based on self-report, compared to evaluations that would normally require a clinician to rate them. Even so issues may arise if participants are required to complete this on their own, because few older adults are truly technologically savvy.

Even when a digital test is created “identically” to the original paper-and-pencil test, it will not necessarily produce the same results (Germine et al., 2018). When testing out the solution it is important to use the same device, the same model, and software, as all these factors can influence performance on certain tests (e.g., reaction time tests). Even more so, ownership of specific digital devices and technologies have been found to be related to the same variables (e.g., education, age, health) that predict performance on tests of reaction time (Germine et al., 2018). Therefore, this variability becomes a confounding variable. Germine and colleagues (2018) exemplifies this using three scenarios: 1. When performance on a test is impaired, but this is due to the longer latency in response time due to the device; 2. Differences in performance between groups, which may be interpreted as cognitive differences, are in fact differences in device characteristics between the

groups (e.g., use of older vs. newer tablets); (3) in repeated assessment, if performance is measured on two (or more occasions) but different devices are used at each time point (e.g., by different clinicians) performance might look as if its changing over time, when in fact neuropsychological function is stable. Coming back to the AAL projects, when thinking about putting the developed software on the market, this issue needs to be highlighted to users, as it's unlikely that they will be installing the software on an identical device as the one that it's been piloted on. Proper resources should be allocated to the validation and collection of normative data when tests are digitalised and are translated across devices, so that these processes won't threaten the validity of digital neuropsychological assessment (Germine et al., 2018).

When intending to create solutions that include wearables or other off the shelf devices, AAL consortia should investigate whether these devices have been tested (and have metrics) on older populations. Even so, they should bear in mind that any additional device is likely to be seen as burden, that limit their independence (Moore et al., 2021). Furthermore, if a smooth “communication” between the software and the paired device is found to be lacking, it will likely quickly negatively influence users opinion of the solution. Abouzahra and Ghasemaghahi (2020) found that even seniors who were initially enthusiastic about specific features of the wearable device, by the second interview were less enthusiastic either because of the difficulties they had with the device. They also found that, even though social influence was a dominant factor for seniors to try the devices, after one week of use, this effect was significantly subsidized. By then seniors were influenced by their own experience with the device and no longer by the effect of others opinions.

Lastly, though much of the literature suggests that older adults are willing to use digital technology there may be barriers associated to the ageing process (e.g., cognitive decline), to various aspects of the technology (e.g., interface usability) (Vaportzis et al., 2017) as well as cultural barriers that need to be taken into account, both when developing such technology and when devising policy for the adoption of such tools.

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